

Preparation of MnO₂@silver-X zeolite nanocomposite adsorbent for the detoxification of toxic blister agent simulant 2-chloroethyl phenyl sulfide (2-CEPS)

Meysam Sadeghi*

Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khorramabad, Iran
Email: meysamsadeghi1364@gmail.com

Sina Yekta

Department of Chemistry, Qaemshahr Branch, Islamic Azad University, Qaemshahr, Iran

Mohammad Mahmoudi Alemi

Department of Chemistry, Golestan University, Gorgan, Iran

Pourya Zarshenas

Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

In this present research, MnO₂ nanoparticles@silver-X zeolite nanocomposite adsorbent was manufactured by the impregnation method and identified using Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Atomic adsorption spectrometry (AAS), X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) techniques. In the next step, the MnO₂@AgX nanocomposite performance for the detoxification of blister agent simulant 2-chloroethyl phenyl sulfide (2-CEPS) was evaluated by applying GC-FID. The GC-FID achieved data displayed that this agent simulant was completely detoxified over the MnO₂@AgX nanocomposite surface in n-hexane solvent after 12h. The both hydrolysis and elimination products namely 2-hydroxyl ethyl phenyl sulfide (2-HEPS) and phenyl vinyl sulfide (PVS) from 2-CEPS molecule were also identified by GC-MS analysis, respectively.

Keywords: MnO₂ nanoparticles@silver-X zeolite, zeolite nanocomposite, 2-CEPS, detoxification, hydrolysis, elimination.